

Welcome and thank you for your participation

Thank you for participating in this experiment regarding reviews of model-based specifications against stakeholder intentions.

Please consider the experiment will last approximately 20-30 minutes.

Please do not use the back button of your browser. It is important that you complete the experiment straightforward.

Review of model-based specifications

On each of the next 4 pages, you will find one model-based specification. The specification will be either

a) a functional design consisting of function network diagrams and state machines

--OR--

b) a set of message sequence charts.

Below each specification you will find natural language stakeholder intentions. Please review the depicted models and decide whether the stakeholder intention is displayed in the specification or not. For each stakeholder intention, please rate your confidence in your decision.

Please review the functional design of a lane keeping support (LKS) with respect to stakeholder intentions

Are following stakeholder intentions represented in the displayed functional design?

Please decide whether you think so, or not. In addition, please rate your confidence in the decision you made.

	yes	no	very confident	very unconfident
The LKS shall determine whether an automated intervention is necessary or not, based on a video stream monitoring the lane and the steering angle.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
In addition, it must be verified that no interventions are conducted if the driver intends to exit the lane. Therefore, it shall be requested, whether the indicator is activated or not.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
To determine the corrected steering angle, instead of the desired steering angle at the steering wheel the actual yaw rate shall be used. Yawrate can be requested from another system.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
In case only minor interventions are needed the LKS shall conduct a steering intervention to the steering wheel, for larger interventions braking shall be used.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
The driver must be able to override automated steering interventions at any time. Therefore, a manual steering command must stop all active intervention (to the wheel and to the brakes).	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
After an intervention was conducted the LKS shall resume monitoring for additional interventions.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
In case yawrate and desired steering angle at the steering wheel differ by more than 10° no intervention shall be conducted as this commonly stems from erroneous data.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Please review the functional design of a door control unit (DCU) with respect to stakeholder intentions

Are following stakeholder intentions represented in the displayed functional design?

Please decide whether you think so, or not. In addition, please rate your confidence in the decision you made.

	yes	no	very confident	very unconfident
The DCU shall detect intrusion attempts from misuse of interior controls and from misuse of the interlocks. In addition, destruction of the car's windows shall be taken into account.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/> <input type="radio"/> <input type="radio"/> <input type="radio"/> <input type="radio"/>	
In case of misuse of the interior control the DCU shall verify that no passenger is inside the car.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/> <input type="radio"/> <input type="radio"/> <input type="radio"/> <input type="radio"/>	
When an intrusion attempt is detected, the car shall engage acoustic and optical warning.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/> <input type="radio"/> <input type="radio"/> <input type="radio"/> <input type="radio"/>	
In addition, the intrusion attempt shall be verified for a second time.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/> <input type="radio"/> <input type="radio"/> <input type="radio"/> <input type="radio"/>	
If the first intrusion attempt stems from a destruction of the car's windows, then the DCU shall immediately initiate an emergency call.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/> <input type="radio"/> <input type="radio"/> <input type="radio"/> <input type="radio"/>	
To allow for emergency calls, the GPS System shall periodically inform the DCU about the current GPS Position.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/> <input type="radio"/> <input type="radio"/> <input type="radio"/> <input type="radio"/>	
In case the engine is running, intrusion detection shall only be conducted if the car is standing and the doors are locked.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/> <input type="radio"/> <input type="radio"/> <input type="radio"/> <input type="radio"/>	

Please review following set of message sequence charts for a lane keeping support (LKS) with respect to stakeholder intentions

Are following stakeholder intentions represented in the displayed message sequence charts?

Please decide whether you think so, or not. In addition, please rate your confidence in the decision you made.

	yes	no	very confident	very unconfident
The LKS shall determine whether an automated intervention is necessary or not, based on a video stream monitoring the lane and the steering angle.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>		
In addition, it must be verified that no interventions are conducted if the driver intends to exit the lane. Therefore, it shall be requested, whether the indicator is activated or not.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	○○○○○	
To determine the corrected steering angle, instead of the desired steering angle at the steering wheel the actual yaw rate shall be used. Yawrate can be requested from another system.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	○○○○○	
In case only minor interventions are needed the LKS shall conduct a steering intervention to the steering wheel, for larger interventions braking shall be used.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	○○○○○	
The driver must be able to override automated steering interventions at any time. Therefore, a manual steering command must stop all active intervention (to the wheel and to the brakes).	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	○○○○○	
After an intervention was conducted the LKS shall resume monitoring for additional interventions.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	○○○○○	
In case yawrate and desired steering angle at the steering wheel differ by more than 10° no intervention shall be conducted as this commonly stems from erroneous data.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	○○○○○	

Please review following set of message sequence charts for a door control unit (DCU) with respect to stakeholder intentions

Are following stakeholder intentions represented in the displayed message sequence charts?

Please decide whether you think so, or not. In addition, please rate your confidence in the decision you made.

	yes	no		very confident	very unconfident
The DCU shall detect intrusion attempts from misuse of interior controls and from misuse of the interlocks. In addition, destruction of the car's windows shall be taken into account.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>		<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
In case of misuse of the interior control the DCU shall verify that no passenger is inside the car.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>		<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
When an intrusion attempt is detected, the car shall engage acoustic and optical warning.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>		<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
In addition, the intrusion attempt shall be verified for a second time.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>		<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
If the first intrusion attempt stems from a destruction of the car's windows, then the DCU shall immediately initiate an emergency call.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>		<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
To allow for emergency calls, the GPS System shall periodically inform the DCU about the current GPS Position.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>		<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
In case the engine is running, intrusion detection shall only be conducted if the car is standing and the doors are locked.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>		<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Please rate your comfort using a review model (reviewing the message sequence charts) instead of the functional design

During your review you partly reviewed the original specification of the **functional design** (function networks and state machines) or a dedicated **review model** (message sequence charts) that displayed the same information as specified in the functional design.
 Within the next questions we want to elicit your opinion on reviewing the review model instead of reviewing the original functional design.

To which extend do you agree with following statements?

	The Review Model (The Message Sequence Charts)					The Original Specification (The Functional Design)
My performance of the manual review is at its best using following model	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
My productivity of the manual review is best supported by reviewing the following model	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
The effectiveness of me performing manual reviews is highest by reviewing following model	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I find following model more useful to perform manual reviews	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
To me the use of the following model in manual reviews is clearer and more understandable than the use of the other	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
The manual review of following model needs less mental effort than the review of the other model	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I find following model easier to use in manual reviews	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
If there was no one around to tell me what to do as I go, I would prefer to manually review following model	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
If someone showed me how to do it first, I would prefer to manually review following model	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Experience and Personal Data

Please rate your experience with following development activities and model notations

	very experienced	very inexperienced
Model-based documentation of requirements	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Development of embedded systems	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Message Sequence Charts	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Models for documenting the functional design	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Finite State Machines	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Conducting reviews of model-based specifications	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Please support us with some personal data, which will be analyzed anonymous

Age years

Gender

Highest educational degree (e.g. Abitur, Bachelor, etc.)

Subject of highest educational degree (e.g. WInf, AI-SE, etc.)

Target educational degree

Subject of target educational degree

Semesters studied in current degree program semesters

Anticipated end of study

Thank you for completing this questionnaire!

We would like to thank you very much for helping us.
 Your answers were transmitted, you may close the browser window or tab now.